

The Influence of Hedonic Shopping Motivation, Fashion Involvement, and Sales Promotion on Impulse Buying in E-commerce Shopee

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ABSTRACT: The marked phenomenon of the fashion industry causes a person to experience behavior by unconsciously buying something without thinking Long or often called impulse buying driven by positive emotions and motivations. In addition to this e-commerce shopee popular today often attempt to make consumer impuls buy behavior based on hedonic shopping motivation, fashion involvement, and sales promotion The objectives of this research are analyze the influence of hedonic Shopping motivation, influence fashion involving, and sales promotion on impuls buying on shopee e- commerce. This research employs a quantitative approach to examine the population of postgraduate and bachelor's students at FEB University of Muhammadiyah Surakarta. Utilizing a purposive sampling technique, this study engaged 100 respondents meeting specific predetermined criteria. The primary data for this research were gathered through questionnaire-based data collection techniques. Smart PLS was utilized as the primary data analysis tool. The results of the analysis of research data show that: hedonic shopping motivation has a positive and significant influence on impulsive buying; fashion involvement has a positive and significant influence on impulsive buying; And sales promotion has a positive and significant impact on impulsive buying.

KEYWORDS: fashion involvement, hedonic shopping motivation, impulse buying, sales promotion, shopee

INTRODUCTION

The fashion industry has grown significantly and become a large and profitable sector. According to Padmasari & Widyastuti (2022), the phenomenon of the proliferation of various products related to fashion appears to be increasingly driven by the desire for individual recognition. This motivates individuals to consciously build their own identity and engage with communities that share similar interests. Participation in current developing trends is often seen as a personal pride, indicating that someone is fashionable or modern because they keep up with the evolution of the fashion world (Mrad et al., 2020).

Shopee currently holds the highest market share in digital marketing in Indonesia, which is one of the online-based sales platforms (Chong & Ali, 2022). One of the reasons for the increased Shopee user base is the convenience offered by various features within the platform for transactions (Mirza & Ali, 2020; Andika et al., 2021). Furthermore, the variety of discounts, cashback, free shipping, and diverse promotional policies by Shopee make it the most preferred e-commerce platform. Continued use of the Shopee e-commerce platform by customers is also linked to their satisfaction with the service (Mbeté & Tanamal, 2020).

There are several factors that make Shopee e-commerce an appropriate subject for impulsive buying research. Firstly, the diversity of products offered by Shopee, ranging from fashion, electronics, cosmetic products, to household equipment (Tumanggor et al., 2022). This product diversity increases the likelihood of buyers making impulsive purchases as they have a significant chance of finding desired products. Additionally, the discounts and promotions offered by Shopee further motivate buyers to make impulsive purchases (Effendi et al., 2020).

The development of shopping centers, malls, and department stores, along with the increasingly modern era, has become a significant driver in raising public awareness of fashion aspects and lifestyle (Brewer, 2019). Meanwhile, Putra et al. (2020) note that this trend plays a role in the growing number of shopping centers offering various fashion choices for both men and women, whether through department stores, boutiques, or factory outlets, with service standards and quality that adhere to the norms in each shopping location.

Profitability in the business world is significantly influenced by impulsive buying behavior (Memon et al., 2019). This prompts business entities to gather relevant information and influence impulsive buying tendencies to develop effective competitive strategies. Mahmudah (2020) reveals that factors such as the lifestyle stage have a significant impact on impulsive buying decisions.

Arfia (2022) posits the definition of Shopping Lifestyle as a series of responses and views of individuals towards directed product purchases. This becomes a key factor driving impulsive buying behavior. In this context, an individual's attitude towards the use of time and money in purchasing goods and services, influenced by various factors such as desires, opinions, brand products, and marketing strategies, can be defined as retail shopping lifestyle. This is a crucial part of understanding and analyzing impulsive buying decisions.

Tirtayasa et al. (2020) found that hedonic shopping motivation, shopping lifestyle, and fashion involvement significantly influence impulse buying. Febrianti et al. (2021) revealed that shopping lifestyle and fashion knowledge are significant factors in impulsive buying. Meanwhile, Saputri (2017) found that fashion involvement does not affect impulse buying.

Umboh et al. (2018) highlighted that shopping lifestyle and fashion involvement do not have a significant partial effect on impulse buying among female consumers in MTC Manado. However, sales promotion has been proven to partially influence impulse buying, and simultaneously, all three factors have a positive effect on impulsive purchases. Wahyuni & Setyawati's (2020) findings indicate that the hedonic buying impulse significantly and positively influences impulsive buying on the Shopee e-commerce platform. These findings suggest that the stronger the Hedonic Shopping Motivation, the greater the impulsive purchases on Shopee.

According to Tyrväinen et al. (2020), hedonic motivation is a quest for satisfaction and efforts made by customers to attain pleasure. Most emotionally involved buyers tend to have hedonic shopping experiences. This emotional drive sometimes triggers impulsive buying. The positive influence of external factors, such as interest in products or sales promotions, can elevate an individual's positive emotions. Fashion involvement refers to the extent to which consumers place importance on the fashion product category, especially clothing (Jin & Ryu, 2019). It encompasses consumer characteristics, shopping habits, and product interest levels, all of which have been proven to strengthen tendencies for hedonic satisfaction, trigger positive emotional responses, and influence unplanned purchases. Fashion closely relates to individual characteristics and knowledge in fashion matters, influenced by consumer beliefs in making purchases (Salem & Alanadoly, 2022).

Sales promotion tends to lead to impulsive buying as it is intended to encourage customers to make instant purchases and test products for a specific period (Gorji & Siami, 2020). One element that can increase sales is promotional media (Sumarwanto, 2021). Furthermore, e-commerce sites that offer adequate promotions can provide external incentives to customers for making purchases (Wiranata & Hananto, 2020).

Research conducted by Ikanubun et al. (2019) revealed relevant results regarding the impact of hedonic shopping motivation on impulsive buying behavior on e-commerce platforms. Safitri et al.'s (2023) study indicates that hedonic shopping motivation is positively and significantly influenced by motivation, promotions, and product quality.

Wijayanto et al.'s (2023) research shows that sales promotions and shopping lifestyles positively affect positive emotions and impulsive purchases. Positive emotions act as a mediator between the two. Another finding by Denia et al. (2023) demonstrates that hedonic shopping and sales promotions impact positive emotions and impulsive buying behavior. In Zahara's (2019) research, sales promotions at ABC Hypermarket impacted impulsive buying, indicating that comprehensive sales campaigns can increase impulsive purchases. Andriani & Harti (2021) found that the discount variable significantly influences impulsive buying, while there is no significant relationship between positive emotions and website quality with impulsive purchases.

Impulsive buying is defined as sudden or unplanned purchasing actions known as buying without careful consideration. Consumer impulsive purchases can result from changes in shopping lifestyles that encompass a wider variety of products (Zhang et al., 2020). Meanwhile, Rook in Nurcholish (2017) defines impulsive buying as unplanned shopping behavior driven by emotions, where decisions are made quickly and without careful consideration of all available information and options.

Based on this background, the author is interested in conducting research titled "The Influence of Hedonic Shopping Motivation, Fashion Involvement, and Sales Promotion on Impulse Buying in E-Commerce Shopee (A Study on FEB and Postgraduate Students at the Muhammadiyah University of Surakarta).

METHODOLOGY

This research employs a quantitative approach with a conclusive research design to test hypotheses and examine relationships from the generated data. The researcher selected the campus of FEB (Faculty of Economics and Business) and the Postgraduate School of Muhammadiyah University of Surakarta as the study location, focusing on Shopee customers. To minimize errors during questionnaire completion, the author gathered a sample of up to 100 FEB and Postgraduate students from Muhammadiyah University of Surakarta who are Shopee users. This study utilizes quantitative methodology, where impulsive buying is the dependent variable, while hedonic shopping motivation, fashion involvement, and sales promotion are the independent variables.

The data analysis method employed in this research is Partial Least Squares (PLS) using SMARTPLS software. The Measurement Model (Outer Model) involves analysis for validity and reliability testing. Convergent validity testing is conducted using Pearson's correlation (r), where a calculated r-value greater than the tabulated r-value indicates the questionnaire item's validity. The Structural Model (Inner Model) involves evaluating the values of R-Squared (R²) and Q-Square (predictive relevance) (Ghozali, 2018). Moreover, hypothesis testing is performed by measuring Path Coefficient (Direct Effect).

RESULT AND ANALYSIS

According to Table 1, it appears that all variable values have reliability scores higher than 0.70. The conclusion drawn from this is that composite reliability has been met, indicating the consistency of each item within the research instrument in measuring its variables. The following is the outer model depicting the correlation of indicators with their respective variables.

The validation and reliability testing using PLS were conducted by analyzing the loading factors of each variable. Below are the loading factors generated from the algorithm testing in PLS.

Table 1. Recapitulation of Composite Reliability

Variable	Composite Reliability	Explanation
<i>Hedonic Shopping Motivation</i>	0,911	Reliable
<i>Fashion Involvement</i>	0,891	Reliable
<i>Sales Promotion</i>	0,921	Reliable
<i>Impulsive Buying</i>	0,941	Reliable

Source: Data Processing in the year 2023

According to Table 2 obtained from the validity test of all variables, it appears that all outer loading values are above 0.70. Therefore, the conclusion drawn is that the research instrument meets the validity test requirements and can be used as a data collection tool.

Table 2. Recapitulation of Outer Loadings

Variable	Item	Outer Loading	Explanation
<i>Hedonic Shopping Motivation (X1)</i>	X1.1	0,789	Valid
	X1.2	0,780	Valid
	X1.3	0,752	Valid
	X1.4	0,843	Valid
	X1.5	0,772	Valid
<i>Fashion Involvement (X2)</i>	X2.1	0,761	Valid
	X2.2	0,710	Valid
	X2.3	0,737	Valid
	X2.4	0,805	Valid
	X2.5	0,725	Valid
	X2.6	0,736	Valid
	X2.7	0,728	Valid

Variable	Item	Outer Loading	Explanation
Sales Promotion (X3)	X2.8	0,795	Valid
	X3.1	0,789	Valid
	X3.2	0,838	Valid
	X3.3	0,857	Valid
	X3.4	0,842	Valid
	X3.5	0,797	Valid
	X3.6	0,786	Valid
	X3.7	0,817	Valid
Impulsive Buying (Y)	Y1.1	0,865	Valid
	Y1.2	0,919	Valid
	Y1.3	0,823	Valid
	Y1.4	0,845	Valid
	Y1.5	0,721	Valid

Source: Data Processing in the year 2023

Figure 1. Outer Model

Source: Data Processing in the year 2023

Table 3. Fornell-Larcker Test Output

Variable	Fashion Involvement	Hedonic Motivation	Impulse Buying	Sales Promotion
Fashion Involvement	0,750			
Hedonic Motivation	0,693	0,788		
Impulse Buying	0,714	0,779	0,837	
Sales Promotion	0,611	0,579	0,637	0,816

Source: Data Processing in the year 2023

According to the findings of the Fornell-Larcker test, the Variable fashion involvement correlates at 0.750, Variable hedonic shopping motivation at 0.788, Variable impulse buying at 0.837, and Variable sales promotion at 0.816. This indicates that each Variable has a high correlation with itself, indicating good cross-loading values.

Table 4. Inner Model Testing Results

Variable	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Q Square
<i>Impulse Buying</i>	0,688	0,679	0,468

Source: Data Processing in the year 2023

The analysis results indicate that the Adjusted R-Square is 0.679. This indicates that Variables such as hedonic shopping motivation, fashion involvement, and sales promotion can explain approximately 67.9% of the variance in the impulse buying construct. Meanwhile, approximately 32.1% of the remaining variance can be explained by additional factors not covered in this study. Furthermore, the Q-Square predictive relevance value is 0.468. This finding illustrates that the model has the ability to explain approximately 46.8% predictive relevance.

Figure 2. Inner Model

Source: Data Processing in the year 2023

Table 5. Hypothesis Testing Output

Variable	Original Sample	T-Statistic	P Values	Explanation
<i>Hedonic Shopping Motivation -> Impulse Buying</i>	0,488	5,793	0,000	Significant and positive
<i>Fashion Involvement -> Impulse Buying</i>	0,254	2,517	0,012	Significant and positive
<i>Sales Promotion -> Impulse Buying</i>	0,199	2,118	0,035	Significant and positive

Source: Data Processing in the year 2023

The analysis results indicate that hedonic shopping motivation significantly influences impulsive buying because the value of the Variable, measured by the t-statistic, is 5.793 > 1.66, and it has a p-value of 0.000 < 0.05. The original sample yields a positive value of 0.488, indicating a positive relationship. Thus, as hedonic shopping motivation increases, impulsive buying also increases.

The variable "fashion involvement" yielded a t-statistic of $2.517 > 1.66$ with a p-value of $0.012 < 0.05$, indicating that fashion involvement significantly influences impulse buying. The original sample obtained a positive value of 0.254, indicating a positive relationship, meaning that the higher the fashion involvement, the higher the impulse buying.

The variable "sales promotion" obtained a t-statistic of 2.118, which is greater than 1.66, with a p-value of $0.035 < 0.05$. Hence, sales promotion significantly influences impulse buying. Additionally, the original sample yielded a positive value of 0.199, indicating a positive relationship. Therefore, more sales promotions correlate with increased impulse buying.

The research findings demonstrate that the higher the hedonistic behavior of Shopee users, the higher the tendency for impulse buying. Based on the respondents' answers, the majority agreed with the statements, indicating that the respondents have a fairly high level of hedonistic motivation.

The advertisements displayed by Shopee, both through the application and social media, instill trust in consumers. The ads provide clear information about the benefits for consumers, such as discounts or new features like COD check, which make it easier for consumers to verify the authenticity of products before making a purchase. Respondents also tend to like products they find on Shopee, even if it's their first encounter, especially when it comes to well-known brands.

Hedonistic shopping motivation can increase consumer trust, even if they have never seen the product firsthand or have just discovered it on Shopee, because consumers shop for relaxation rather than necessity. Consumers expect to enjoy themselves, feel comfortable, and do something special for themselves when shopping on Shopee with hedonistic motivations. Hedonistic shopping motivations tend to lead to adventurous shopping, where consumers seek joy without considering more efficient purchases.

Consumer enjoyment of brands and following fashion trends are also strong reasons for consumer impulse buying behavior. The fear of missing out on trends creates a sense of competition with others to have the latest items or experiences that are in vogue (Safitri et al., 2023). This is evidenced by the respondents' enthusiasm when viewing Shopee ads. If they find an item they like, their level of agreement with the item indicates that the respondents are likely to make an immediate purchase.

The research findings prove that the higher the hedonistic behavior of female Shopee users in fashion products, the stronger the affirmation of their identity within their social circles. The convenience offered by Shopee also fosters this hedonistic motivation because the increasing online consumer behavior leads to unplanned online purchases (Edelia & Angraini, 2022). These findings support Denia et al. (2023), demonstrating that hedonic shopping motivation substantially and positively influences impulse buying.

The research results confirm that as consumers' fashion involvement increases, their impulse buying behavior also intensifies. Respondents believe that their involvement in fashion contributes to increased happiness because their clothing reflects their personalities. They perceive that being involved in fashion trends gives them the chance to find clothing suitable for their daily activities. Additionally, it boosts their confidence and attracts attention when they wear clothes they like.

This corresponds to the increased impulse buying behavior, as they constantly seek social validation regarding their dressing style, continuously updating their wardrobe with trending clothing. Fashion involvement is closely linked to impulsive buying (Chauhan et al., 2023). Students tend to engage in more impulsive buying compared to other age groups due to their higher fashion involvement. Their greater expertise in accessing and evaluating others triggers impulse buying, particularly in online shopping, where feedback-based websites serve as more efficient platforms for consumer information exchange.

The respondents' desire to delve deeper into various topics related to fashion products brings them joy. To achieve their self-actualization goals, customers must have the confidence to be motivated to follow fashion trends, look good, and behave impulsively. These findings support Edelia & Angraini (2022), Padmasari & Widayastuti (2022), and Tirtayasa et al. (2020), indicating that fashion involvement substantially and positively influences impulse buying.

The research findings indicate that the more frequently promotions are targeted at consumers, the higher the impulse buying behavior. Shopee often offers promotions through discount vouchers and free shipping. Respondents mention that they frequently use vouchers when sellers conduct live streaming on the Shopee app, allowing sellers to provide these vouchers for potential buyers for free.

These vouchers are considered highly beneficial as they reduce the product prices and shipping costs charged by Shopee, making consumers less concerned about higher prices. Flash sale promotions also exist, where specific items are displayed on Shopee at very low prices. Shopee maintains product originality with features like Shopee COD and check-first, allowing consumers to ensure that the received package matches the purchased item before payment.

Shopee's promotions stimulate continuous purchasing behavior among consumers as one buyer can obtain various different vouchers daily, especially the shipping vouchers, which are always eagerly anticipated and utilized by consumers. These sales promotion strategies undeniably benefit Shopee and logistics services. Regardless of factors like age, gender, income, or occupation, customers prefer availing themselves of sales promotion offers, feeling extremely comfortable as they save money and time simultaneously. This research is supported by Masitoh et al. (2022), showing that sales promotions have a positive and significant impact on impulse buying.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the research results indicating a positive and significant influence of Hedonic Shopping Motivation, Fashion Involvement, and Sales Promotion on Impulse Buying behavior on the Shopee E-Commerce platform, it is crucial to enhance promotional strategies to sustain purchasing interest. Additionally, attention should be paid to users' shopping experience in terms of visual aspects, comfort, and application navigation to maintain consumer interest. Researchers also suggest that future studies include a larger sample size than this study because hypotheses would be more robustly supported by the research analysis with a larger sample.

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